

Analysis of Neutrophil-To-Lymphocyte Ratio (NLR) Examination Results in Patients with Pelvic Inflammatory Disease (PID)

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ABSTRACT

Pelvic Inflammatory Disease (PID) is a polymicrobial infection of the upper genital tract that can lead to serious complications such as infertility due to tubal damage, ectopic pregnancy, and chronic pelvic pain. Diagnosing PID is often challenging because its symptoms are nonspecific and there is no single accurate laboratory marker. One biomarker that has increasingly gained attention is the Neutrophil-to-Lymphocyte Ratio (NLR) as an indicator of systemic inflammation. This literature review aims to evaluate the diagnostic value of NLR in patients with PID through an analysis of clinical and mechanistic studies. Literature searches were conducted using the PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar databases. The results show that NLR is significantly elevated in patients with PID compared to healthy controls, reflecting the predominance of acute inflammatory processes characterized by increased neutrophils and decreased lymphocytes due to immunological stress. The Neutrophil-to-Lymphocyte Ratio (NLR) is an accurate inflammatory marker with high sensitivity and specificity; it is simple, inexpensive, and accessible through routine blood tests, making it a potentially valuable diagnostic tool for Pelvic Inflammatory Disease (PID).

KEYWORDS: Pelvic Inflammatory Disease, NLR, Review

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I. INTRODUCTION

Pelvic Inflammatory Disease (PID), which involves inflammation and infection of the upper female genital tract (the endometrium, fallopian tubes, and ovaries), remains a major reproductive health problem¹. This condition is often caused by ascending polymicrobial infections or sexually transmitted infections, particularly *Chlamydia trachomatis* and *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*². Acute morbidity and long-term consequences, such as ectopic pregnancy, chronic pelvic pain, and tubal factor infertility, are caused by PID³. The diagnosis of Pelvic Inflammatory Disease (PID) is usually made through clinical assessment; however, no specific physical findings or laboratory tests can accurately identify PID⁴. White blood cell (WBC) count, erythrocyte

sedimentation rate (ESR), and C-reactive protein (CRP) levels are often measured when PID is suspected⁴. The measurement of blood cell subtype ratios may have diagnostic significance for inflammation-related diseases. The neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR), an inflammatory marker, has been found to be predictive in the preoperative diagnosis of TOA and in assessing treatment outcomes in PID⁵.

An increased white blood cell count indicates signs of inflammation and infection, which can be observed in Pelvic Inflammatory Disease (PID). Pelvic Inflammatory Disease (PID) is characterized by neutrophil and T-lymphocyte infiltration in inflammatory lesions and by elevated neutrophil levels in the blood⁶. Excessive white blood cell

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(WBC) levels are useful in confirming the diagnosis of acute PID. However, leukocytosis is observed in only 60% of individuals with acute PID⁷.

The neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR), which has higher sensitivity and specificity than the white blood cell (WBC) count and similar sensitivity and specificity to neutrophil count, plays an important role in the diagnosis of PID. The sensitivity (80.3%) and specificity (78.7%) of NLR are close to those of neutrophil count, which is an important inflammatory marker, making NLR the second most valuable marker after neutrophil count in the diagnosis of PID⁸.

The literature on the analysis of the neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) in patients with Pelvic Inflammatory Disease (PID) is comprehensively reviewed in this study. This research presents a targeted study design, evaluates the quality of clinical data, and synthesizes mechanistic evidence.

II. METHOD

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A. Review Design and Rationale

We employed an integrative narrative review design due to the anticipated scarcity of direct studies. This approach included a focused search for clinical studies reporting the analysis of the neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) as an inflammatory marker in PID or closely related pelvic infections.

B. Search Strategy

The databases searched were Google Scholar, Scopus, and PubMed/MEDLINE. High-impact journals and reviews on the analysis of the neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) in patients with Pelvic Inflammatory Disease (PID) were included. Search terms such as “pelvic inflammatory disease” OR “PID,” “neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio” OR “NLR,” and “leukocytes OR WBC OR inflammatory markers” were used, combining PID with laboratory examinations that serve as inflammatory markers. Publications from 2015 to 2025 were the primary focus; highly relevant foundational studies (before 2015) were considered for mechanistic context only.

C. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion: Included studies were mechanistic human research examining neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) levels in Pelvic Inflammatory Disease (PID), as well as observational or clinical intervention studies evaluating hematological parameters as inflammatory markers in PID. **Exclusion:** Excluded materials included case reports without laboratory analysis, non-peer-reviewed commentaries, and studies outside the scope of hematological parameters.

D. Data Extraction and Quality Assessment

Data extraction was conducted to gather essential information from each article that met the inclusion criteria. The articles reviewed discussed the analysis of the Neutrophil-to-Lymphocyte Ratio (NLR) and Pelvic Inflammatory Disease (PID). Extracted data included the authors' names, year of publication, study design, sample size, mean NLR values, as well as the study results and conclusions.

E. Synthesis Approach

The findings were organized narratively using the following thematic sections to address heterogeneity: (1) clinical evidence involving the collection of laboratory examination data related to the analysis of the neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) in patients with Pelvic Inflammatory Disease (PID); and (2) the integration of empirical results and theoretical frameworks regarding the role of NLR as an inflammatory indicator in PID.

III. RESULT

A. Definition and Basic Concepts of PID

Pelvic Inflammatory Disease (PID) is a polymicrobial infectious condition⁸ involving acute or subclinical infections of the upper female genital tract (ascending), which may involve one or several organs such as the uterus, fallopian tubes, and ovaries. This infection is often accompanied by the spread of inflammation to surrounding pelvic organs. The involvement of these various structures can lead to several pathological conditions, including salpingitis, endometritis, oophoritis, peritonitis, and tubo-ovarian abscess⁴. Genital tract infections in PID can cause damage to the oviducts, and the healing process involves the formation of scar tissue and adhesions, which ultimately increase the risk of tubal factor infertility and ectopic pregnancy⁶.

B. Pathophysiology of PID

The clinical manifestations of PID vary from mild to severe, and mild symptoms can sometimes make the diagnosis challenging⁸. Initially, PID begins with the entry of pathogenic organisms from the vagina into the endocervix. From there, the organisms spread to the endometrium, fallopian tubes, and ovaries. These organisms invade the tissues and trigger the body's response, primarily a local immune reaction characterized by the activation of epithelial cells, macrophages, and neutrophils. These cells then release several pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β), interleukin-6 (IL-6), and tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), which are responsible for recruiting additional leukocytes to the site infected by the organisms^{9 10 11}.

In *Chlamydia trachomatis* infection, the immune response is typically chronic and persistent because *Chlamydia trachomatis* is an intracellular bacterium capable

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of evading phagocytosis. Repeated activation of macrophages and T lymphocytes leads to the release of inflammatory mediators, which can consequently damage epithelial tissues at the site of invasion. If the invasion occurs in the fallopian tubes, the tubal epithelium may be damaged, inducing fibrosis and adhesion formation^{12,13}. In contrast, *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* behaves differently; this organism causes acute inflammation in which the immune response is dominated by neutrophils and the formation of purulent exudate¹⁴.

The increased infiltration of neutrophils and the resulting local tissue damage lead to the release of several enzymes, such as myeloperoxidase, elastase, and acid phosphatase. These enzymes further worsen the ongoing inflammation. The inflammatory process is not only localized but also triggers another response systemic inflammation which is characterized by an increase in circulating neutrophils and a decrease in lymphocyte levels due to immunological stress and elevated cortisol levels^{8,4}.

Figure 1. Pathophysiology of Pelvic Inflammatory Disease and its consequences.

C. Etiology of PID

PID is a complex infectious syndrome characterized by polymicrobial inflammation of the upper female genital tract. The etiology of PID is not limited to a single agent but is instead the result of interactions among pathogenic microorganisms, host factors, and the vaginal microbiota¹⁵.

D. Primary Infectious Agents and Ascending Mechanism

Most cases of PID are caused by ascending sexually transmitted infections (STIs), in which microorganisms migrate from the vagina to the endocervix, and subsequently to the endometrium and fallopian tubes⁶. The most common etiological agents are two pathogens, *Chlamydia trachomatis* and *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, which possess different invasive and intracellular immune evasion mechanisms but both lead to tissue damage^{16,17}.

Chlamydia trachomatis is an obligate intracellular bacterium that causes chronic inflammation through cytokine activation derived from macrophages, such as IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α , as well as by inducing endothelial molecule expression¹⁸. This process leads to lymphocyte and

neutrophil infiltration, followed by tubal epithelial damage and scarring^{19,20}. In some cases, *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* causes acute inflammation with a rapid neutrophilic immune response, resulting in pus formation and purulent exudate in acute PID^{21,22}. Synergistic interactions between these two microorganisms are frequently observed in dual infections (coinfections), increasing the risk of complications such as tubo-ovarian abscess and fallopian tube-related infertility^{23,24}.

E. Secondary and Polymicrobial Infectious Agents

PID is not always associated with classical sexually transmitted diseases. Many clinical cases demonstrate the presence of mixed aerobic and anaerobic flora, such as *Mycoplasma genitalium*, *Ureaplasma urealyticum*, *Gardnerella vaginalis*, *Bacteroides* spp., and *Peptostreptococcus* spp.^{25,26} These microorganisms contribute to prolonged inflammation through the release of toxins, biofilm formation, and proteases that inhibit epithelial regeneration. *Mycoplasma genitalium* is considered an emerging significant pathogen in PID, with a prevalence of 15–30% among patients with endometritis or salpingitis in the absence of gonococcal or *Chlamydia trachomatis* infection^{25,27}. This pathogen has a high adhesion capacity to cervical and tubal epithelium through MgpB/MgpC proteins, causing persistent subclinical inflammation that is difficult to detect clinically.

F. Host Factors and Mucosal

Immunity Susceptibility to PID is determined by host factors. Conditions such as young age (under 25 years), multiple sexual partners, deficiencies in local cervical mucosal immunity, and hormonal changes that reduce protective mucus play an important role in facilitating pathogen colonization^{28,29}. The reproductive immune system must maintain a complex balance between tolerance and defense. Excessive activation of the innate immune system (neutrophils, macrophages, and NK cells) results in the release of excessive pro-inflammatory cytokines, which can exacerbate local tissue damage³⁰. This condition also explains the increased neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) in PID patients, indicating a dominance of acute inflammation over adaptive immune responses^{8,31}.

G. Non-Sexual and Iatrogenic

Mechanisms Although most PID cases are associated with sexual transmission, non-sexual etiologies are also identified, particularly as a result of invasive medical procedures such as IUD insertion, curettage, or hysterosalpingography performed without adequate asepsis³². Hematogenous spread from systemic infections (such as *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*) can also lead to tuberculous salpingitis, although this condition has become increasingly rare^{33,34}.

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H. Modern Etiological Perspective: PID as a Spectrum of Dysbiosis

The etiological concept of PID has now shifted from a single-infection model to one involving reproductive microbiota dysbiosis. Imbalances in the vaginal microbiota (for example, *Gardnerella* dominance or reduced *Lactobacillus crispatus*) can increase vaginal pH, impair mucus production, and facilitate the colonization of ascending pathogens^{35 36}. Therefore, modern PID is viewed as an inflammatory spectrum resulting from a combination of infection, dysbiosis, and local immune dysregulation.

I. NLR as a Laboratory Diagnostic Tool for PID

Early diagnosis of PID is crucial so that antibiotic therapy can be initiated promptly, thereby preventing complications such as infertility due to tubal damage (tubal factor infertility), ectopic pregnancy, and chronic pelvic pain¹⁵. The subtle and highly variable symptoms of PID often make the diagnosis challenging and may even require surgical evaluation for confirmation. Early diagnosis can prevent inflammatory complications and infertility in women. Therefore, it is important to investigate biomarkers for the early diagnosis of PID⁶

Laparoscopy is considered the gold standard in diagnosing PID, but it is not recommended as an initial examination because it is invasive and costly. No laboratory parameter specifically indicates the severity of PID to the extent that surgical intervention is required. Compared with laparoscopy, clinical diagnosis alone has a predictive value of only 65–90%, and therefore must be supported by additional examinations, including microbiological tests, CRP levels, and leukocyte counts. Although these parameters are not specific, they may assist in establishing the diagnosis of PID³⁷.

To date, no single method or combination of tests can consistently and accurately detect PID. Examinations such as white blood cell count (WBC), erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), and C-reactive protein (CRP) are commonly performed when PID is suspected. However, these results may still fall within normal ranges, leading to missed or inadvertent misdiagnosis⁴. CRP levels are known to rise alongside ESR³⁸.

Erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), C-reactive protein (CRP), and CA-125 have been previously investigated and shown to have comparable diagnostic ability in establishing the diagnosis of PID. However, none of these markers provide a meaningful improvement in diagnostic value beyond what can be determined through medical history-taking and physical examination. Additionally, because these tests cannot be obtained rapidly, their practical usefulness in assessing patients suspected of having PID is limited¹⁵.

Several other diagnostic methods have also been explored, one of which is measuring serum LOXL2 concentration. LOXL2 is essential for the formation of

fibrous connective tissue and for the stability of the extracellular matrix (ECM)³⁹. Based on findings from⁶, serum LOXL2 expression levels were found to be elevated in patients with PID compared with healthy controls, and were also higher in PID patients with pelvic adhesions than in those without adhesions. Assessment of AMH levels may also be performed in patients with PID. PID patients with bilateral fallopian tube obstruction show decreased AMH hormone levels, suggesting that chronic PID has the potential to reduce ovarian reserve⁴⁰.

A negative endometrial biopsy for endometritis can rule out upper genital tract infection with a negative predictive value of 90%. However, because it requires pathological expertise and the results are not rapidly available, this procedure is rarely used routinely and has a limited role in guiding initial therapy for patients suspected of having PID¹⁵. Another diagnostic method is Procalcitonin (PCT), which is known to be rapid and specific for infections in critically ill patients, and is already used in routine diagnostic panels. However, PCT is relatively expensive⁴¹.

This study focuses on the use of NLR as a diagnostic tool, which has its own advantages in detecting inflammation, particularly PID. NLR is the ratio between two types of leukocytes, namely neutrophils and lymphocytes. The presence of neutrophils and plasma cells in endometrial tissue can serve as markers of PID and has been compared with laparoscopy as a diagnostic method¹⁵. Leukocytes, which are essential components of the immune system known for their role in protecting the body from infection and facilitating immune responses, also play a significant role in various physiological processes within the female reproductive system.

The female reproductive system undergoes cyclical changes influenced by hormonal fluctuations, which require precise regulation by immune cells. Leukocytes contribute significantly to this regulation, participating in processes such as follicular development, ovulation, menstruation, and tissue remodeling. Their ability to release cytokines, chemokines, and growth factors enables them to interact closely with reproductive tissues, influence cellular activity, and maintain homeostasis⁴².

An example of a brief case history involves a 29-year-old patient who presented to the gynecology clinic with increased vaginal discharge for two weeks. She reported lower abdominal pain, fever, and chills over the past two days. Supporting examinations showed an increase in greenish vaginal discharge. An endocervical and intravaginal swab was obtained using a speculum. Vaginal palpation revealed cervical motion tenderness and severe tenderness on palpation of the right adnexa. Laboratory tests showed elevated leukocyte levels (17,000/ μ L).

Another case report involved a 32-year-old female patient from Italy who presented with pelvic pain and fever in April 2017. Previously, she had been treated for pelvic pain and

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received antibiotic therapy for suspected PID. The patient experienced a mild fever, and blood test results showed hemoglobin levels of 11.8 g/dL, a total leukocyte count of $12.26 \times 10^9/L$, and neutrophils at 92.2%⁴³.

Another study reported that leukocyte counts were elevated in 104 patients (65.82%), indicating a trend of increasing leukocytosis in the group with more severe conditions³⁷. NLR is one of the inflammatory markers that has been shown to possess predictive value in the preoperative diagnosis of tubo-ovarian abscess (TOA)⁴⁴ as well as in assessing treatment outcomes in PID⁵. NLR is an inflammatory marker known to have a strong association with inflammatory processes. Neutrophils are the first population of leukocytes to migrate to the site of infection and influence the body's inflammatory response. Acute inflammation or bacterial infection increases neutrophil production and the infiltration of inflammatory cells^{5, 45}. PID is characterized by neutrophil and T-lymphocyte infiltration in inflammatory lesions, along with elevated neutrophil counts in the blood⁶.

Findings from the study by⁴ revealed a statistically significant difference between the patient group and the control group in terms of NLR values ($p < 0.001$). Based on ROC curve analysis, with a cut-off value of 1.9, NLR could predict PID with a sensitivity of 79.2% and a specificity of 60%. Another study also found a strong association between PID and NLR, reporting that with a cut-off value of 2.92, NLR had a sensitivity of 81.5% and a specificity of 98.4%. NLR is a useful marker for monitoring treatment response⁵. Another study by⁴⁴ reported that NLR demonstrated a high ability to predict tubo-ovarian abscess (TOA), with a sensitivity of 95.2% and a specificity of 99.4%. In addition, the positive predictive value (PPV) reached 99.2%, while the negative predictive value (NPV) was 96.7%. Considering that TOA is one of the severe complications of PID, the high sensitivity and specificity of NLR in that study are likely due to the greater severity of cases compared with the present study.

Findings from study⁸ indicate that the sensitivity of NLR is comparable to elevated leukocyte counts, yet it demonstrates higher specificity in establishing a diagnosis of PID. In addition, the sensitivity and specificity of NLR are nearly equivalent to neutrophil counts, which are recognized as a primary inflammatory marker, making NLR the second most valuable diagnostic indicator after neutrophil count in detecting PID. NLR values were significantly higher in the PID patient group compared with the control group ($p < 0.001$). It was found that NLR had the second-highest sensitivity (80.3%) and specificity (78.7%) after neutrophil count among all complete blood count (CBC) parameters. Thus, NLR has higher sensitivity and specificity in diagnosing PID compared with WBC, PDW, PLR, and MPV, which have also been evaluated as inflammatory markers in recent studies. These findings suggest that NLR

is a highly valuable inflammatory marker and can be used in the diagnosis of PID. Compared with similar studies, the larger sample size in this study may be considered a major strength.

In another study investigating the diagnostic value of CBC parameters and CRP in PID cases,⁴⁶ it was found that NLR had the highest sensitivity and specificity in diagnosing PID and showed sensitivity and specificity comparable to CRP. They concluded that NLR can be used alongside other CBC parameters to aid in the diagnosis of PID. NLR is an inexpensive and simple parameter derived from routine blood tests. Its use as an inflammatory marker has shown a good correlation with C-reactive protein (CRP)⁴⁷. Study⁴¹ concluded that NLR, with a cut-off value of 6.2, had a sensitivity of 91% and a specificity of 96% for patients with bacteremia. Another study⁴⁸ demonstrated that NLR can serve as a predictor of bacteremia in patients presenting to the emergency department.

Table 1. Predictive Value of NLR for the Diagnosis of PID According to Various Studies.

No.	Penulis, tahun	Journal	Desain studi	AUC	Cut-off	Sensitivitas	Spesifitas	Referensi
1.	Aliyeva, 2019	Istanbul Medical Journal	Retrospective	0.864	2.58	80.3	78.7	Aliyeva S, Kayi S, Soyman Z, Ateser G, Bacanakkil H, Ilcan B. Diagnostic Value of Hematological Parameters in Pelvic Inflammatory Disease. Istanbul Med J. 2019 Oct 24;20(5):482-6.
2.	Seçkin, 2015	Gynecology, Obstetrics & Reproductive Medicine	Retrospective	0.915	2.674	87	82	Seçkin KD, Karlı MF, Yücel B, Özköse B, Yıldırım D, Çetin BA, et al. Neutrophil Lymphocyte Ratio, Platelet Erythrocyte Ratio and Mean Platelet Volume, which one is More Predictive in the Diagnosis of Pelvic Inflammatory Disease? Gynecology Obstetrics & Reproductive Medicine. 21(3):151-4.
3.	Hicsoğlu, 2019	Clinical and Experimental Obstetrics & Gynecology	Retrospective	0.78	1.9	79.2	60	Hicsoğlu M, Turpat A, Akdemir E, Usta A, Erenöz AA, Karaman A. Predictive value of neutrophil to lymphocyte ratio, lymphocyte to monocyte ratio and mean platelet volume for pelvic inflammatory disease. Clin Exp Obstet Gynecol. 2019 Feb 10;46(1):36-41.

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4.	Yildirim, 2015	Gynecologic and Obstetric Investigation	Retrospective	0.99	4.15	95.2	99.4	Yildirim M, Turkyilmaz E, Asar AF. Preoperative Neutrophil-to-Lymphocyte Ratio Has a Better Predictive Capacity in Diagnosing Tubo-Ovarian Abscess. Gynecol Obstet Invest. 2015;80(4):234-9.
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IV. DISCUSSION

Based on various studies, NLR has been proven to possess strong diagnostic value in detecting PID. The majority of studies reported AUC values above 0.80, indicating good discriminative ability between patients with and without pelvic infection. Sensitivity ranged from 79% to 95%, while specificity varied between 60% and 99.4%. The studies with the highest AUC values were conducted in populations with severe inflammation, such as cases of tubo-ovarian abscess, in which physiological increases in neutrophil counts and decreases in lymphocytes result in significantly elevated NLR values. Conversely, studies reporting lower AUC and specificity were likely influenced by data heterogeneity, differences in diagnostic criteria, and variations in sample collection techniques

Clinically, NLR offers several advantages: it is easy to obtain, inexpensive, and available through routine blood tests. However, the use of NLR as a standalone diagnostic tool is not recommended. NLR is most effective when used as a supporting parameter in combination with clinical assessment, other laboratory tests (such as CRP and leukocyte count), and imaging studies. In this way, NLR can make a meaningful contribution to the initial management of patients with suspected PID.

The inflammatory process in PID generally begins with an ascending infection that spreads from the vagina to the endocervix, then to the endometrium and eventually the fallopian tubes. The invasion of microorganisms stimulates activation of the local immune system, primarily through the roles of epithelial cells, macrophages, and neutrophils. These cells subsequently release various pro-inflammatory cytokines such as interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β), interleukin-6 (IL-6), and tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), which function to recruit additional leukocytes to the site of infection^{9 11 10}

Infection caused by *Chlamydia trachomatis* typically leads to chronic inflammation because this bacterium is intracellular and able to evade phagocytosis. Repeated activation of macrophages and T lymphocytes results in the continuous release of inflammatory mediators, ultimately damaging the epithelial tissue at the site of infection. When this process occurs in the fallopian tubes, epithelial damage may progress to fibrosis and adhesion^{12 13}. In contrast,

infection caused by *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* generally triggers acute inflammation characterized by neutrophil dominance and the formation of purulent exudate¹⁴.

Increased neutrophil infiltration in infected tissues leads to the release of various enzymes, including myeloperoxidase, elastase, and acid phosphatase, which contribute to worsening tissue damage and amplifying the systemic inflammatory response. This condition is associated with elevated neutrophil counts and decreased lymphocyte levels in the bloodstream, which is reflected in an increased neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) as an indicator of inflammation in patients with PID^{4 8}

As a result of neutrophil activation due to tissue damage, there is an increased release of enzymes such as myeloperoxidase, acid phosphatase, and elastase, which leads to neutrophil predominance and consequently elevates the NLR value. The differences in NLR findings between studies⁴ and ⁵ are attributable to variations in the study populations, where study⁵ involved hospitalized patients with potentially more severe PID, whereas study⁴ included patients with varying levels of PID severity, both inpatient and outpatient.

PID is a polymicrobial infection condition⁸, which can be acute and may lead to various pathological conditions⁴. Pathological conditions can result in increased levels of the hormone prolactin. Immune system cells, such as macrophages, NK cells, T lymphocytes, and B lymphocytes, are producers of prolactin. Some evidence suggests that prolactin acts as a growth factor for lymphocytes and stimulates the immune response. Furthermore, almost all hematopoietic cells possess prolactin receptors on their cell surface. Elevated prolactin levels can cause changes in immune status under pathological conditions. The action of prolactin begins with its binding to specific membrane receptors, where prolactin receptors are present on immune cells and belong to the cytokine receptor family, such as IL-2, IL-3, IL-4, IL-6, IL-7 receptors, growth hormone, and erythropoietin receptors. Prolactin acts as a pro-inflammatory cytokine by increasing the production of IFN- γ , IL-12, and IL-1 β in peritoneal macrophages. Prolactin also enhances the production of IFN- γ and TNF- α in T cells and mononuclear cells^{47 41}.

Neutrophils are an important subset of leukocytes that play a role in regulating the inflammatory response. Their increased levels are often associated with the development and severity of the inflammatory response. Leukocytes are a vital component of the body's immune function. At the same time, stress hormones such as catecholamines and cortisol increase in the body, which can further reduce lymphocyte counts. Therefore, the NLR becomes an inflammatory index that reflects these two important systems simultaneously and has good clinical value. In this context, neutrophils, lymphocytes, NLR, and PLR are used as valuable inflammatory markers⁴⁹.

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NLR is a cheap, easily obtainable parameter that does not require special equipment. Changes in the WBC population occur rapidly and reflect the role of neutrophils in the early phase of inflammation. In bacterial infections, neutrophils increase (neutrophilia) and lymphocytes decrease (lymphocytopenia). Lymphocytopenia occurs because the body suppresses adaptive immunity to prioritize the innate immune response. Data show that the most affected lymphocytes in severe bacterial infections and sepsis are CD4+ T cells. There are several conditions that reduce the diagnostic value of NLR. This means that, under certain circumstances, the neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio can no longer be used as an accurate marker for detecting bacterial infection, such as in conditions with neutropenia. NLR becomes invalid because the neutrophil count is already low from the outset. Conditions that inherently cause lymphocytopenia also affect NLR. If a patient has a disease that reduces lymphocyte counts, NLR cannot reflect acute infection. Similarly, in conditions of lymphocytosis, where lymphocytes are elevated, NLR becomes falsely low and cannot be used to detect other bacterial infections⁴¹.

Neutrophil activation caused by tissue damage leads to increased release of enzymes such as myeloperoxidase, acid phosphatase, and elastase, resulting in neutrophil dominance and elevated NLR. Study⁵ reported that the neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) was significantly higher in patients diagnosed with PID compared to the control group before treatment. In these patients, clinical improvement was accompanied by a regression of NLR to normal levels after treatment. NLR can be used as a marker of clinical improvement in PID. It can also be used together with other CBC parameters in the diagnosis of PID⁴.

PID is a complex polymicrobial interaction resulting from the interplay between pathogenic microorganisms, reproductive factors, and the reproductive microbiota⁵⁰. Two main pathogens, *Chlamydia trachomatis* and *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, have different pathogenic mechanisms but are both associated with tubal tissue damage. *C. trachomatis* is an obligate intracellular bacterium that causes chronic inflammation through the activation of macrophages and proinflammatory cytokines (IL-1 β , IL-6, TNF- α)⁵¹, whereas *N. gonorrhoeae* induces acute inflammation characterized by neutrophil dominance and the purulent exudate typical of PID⁵². Coinfection with these two pathogens increases the risk of serious complications such as tubo-ovarian abscess and infertility due to fallopian tube damage^{23 24}. However, recent studies indicate that PID cases are not directly associated with gonococcal or chlamydial effects. *Mycoplasma genitalium*, *Ureaplasma urealyticum*, *Gardnerella vaginalis*, *Bacteroides* spp., and *Peptostreptococcus* spp. are examples of pathogens that cause inflammation^{25 53}. *M. genitalium*, in particular, has been identified as an emerging pathogen with a prevalence of 15–30% in patients with non-gonococcal endometritis or

salpingitis. This pathogen possesses MgpB/MgpC adhesion proteins that play a key role in colonizing the cervical and tubal epithelium, triggering persistent subclinical inflammation that is difficult to detect⁵⁴.

In addition to infectious factors, host susceptibility plays an important role in the pathogenesis of PID⁵⁵. Young age (<25 years), sexual behavior involving multiple partners, and deficiencies in cervical mucosal immunity due to hormonal changes are factors that facilitate pathogen colonization. Imbalances in the local immune system, particularly hyperactivation of innate immunity (neutrophils, macrophages, and NK cells), lead to excessive proinflammatory cytokine release and exacerbate local tissue damage²⁰. Non-sexual etiologies also contribute, although less frequently. Invasive medical procedures, such as the insertion of intrauterine devices (IUDs), curettage, and hysterosalpingography without strict asepsis, can serve as entry points for bacteria into the upper genital tract^{56 57}.

V. CONCLUSION

NLR is significantly elevated in patients with PID compared to healthy control groups, reflecting the dominance of acute inflammatory processes characterized by increased neutrophils and decreased lymphocytes due to immunological stress. The neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) is an accurate inflammatory marker with high sensitivity and specificity. It is simple, inexpensive, and accessible through routine blood tests, making it a potential valuable diagnostic tool for Pelvic Inflammatory Disease (PID).

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